

AN ASSESSMENT OF TENANTS SATISFACTION IN STUDENTS HOSTELS IN AWKA

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ABSTRACT

Students' hostels play a crucial role in providing accommodation for students pursuing higher education in any part of the world. The growing student population in Awka, Anambra State in Nigeria due to the presence of Nnamdi Azikiwe University and other notable tertiary institutions, has increased the demand for quality housing in tertiary institutions. Currently hostels face issues of safety, quality, and affordability, affecting students, academic success and well-being. Despite TETFUND's plans to construct new hostels in 2024, only 15% of students live on campus, facing security risks and high off-campus costs. The research aim was to provide an assessment of tenants' satisfaction in student hostels within and around Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Nigeria. The research objectives include: to establish categories of student hostels in Awka, to assess the current level of tenant satisfaction in different students hostels in Awka, to identify factors influencing tenant satisfaction in students hostels in Awka and to identify areas of improving the level of tenant satisfaction in students hostels in Awka. The scope of the study was limited to coverage of public and private hostels within and outside Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The population of the study is a total number of public and private hostels in Awka. The study adopted research survey method to elicit data from students, hence primary and secondary data was used for the research study. Taro Yamane formula was used to determine the sample size for both public and private hostel. 366 questionnaire were distributed and 337 was retrieved representing 92.7% responses. Findings revealed that the facilities amongst those living in private hostels had 20.5% basic setups, 35.3% had standard accommodations, and 8.0% enjoy premium conditions. Conversely, Public hostels exhibit a higher proportion of basic facilities (23.7%), but fewer students (11.6%) have standard amenities, and only 0.9% have access to premium facilities. Key areas of dissatisfaction includes room size layout, hygiene issues, facilities quality etc. To improve tenant satisfaction in students hostels, the study recommended areas for improvement for both private and public hostels which include increasing room comfort, ensuring cleanliness and hygiene, bolstering safety and security, upgrading furniture quality, minimizing noise levels, providing reliable utilities and effective management practices such as establishing clear hostel policies and balanced tenancy agreements and flexibility in visiting hours for public hostels

Keywords: Student's hostels, assessment, tenant satisfaction, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

INTRODUCTION

In the past, students who reside with their wards outside the state are those who opt for hostel accommodations in tertiary institutions. In recent times, students who also reside in the same state where they gained admission also opt for hostel accommodations in tertiary institutions. When young people gain admission into tertiary institutions, it is a common phenomenon to live separate from their parental home, this is to enable them concentrate fully on their chosen course of study. Regardless of an increased housing facility around tertiary institutions, student hostels still remain in high demand primarily because of affordability and nearness to lecture halls. With regard to university adaptation and experience as well as personal character development, most researchers came to similar conclusions that these aspects are in relation with student housing. A well designed hostel accommodation to student's satisfaction and comfort encourages shared interests and positive educational results (Idowu, Shamang and Malachy, 2024).

Chukwu, Okwudiri and Nwankwo (2023) highlighted that many hostel managers are not adequately trained in customer service or conflict resolution, which exacerbates tenant frustrations. Tenant satisfaction in student hostels is not just about providing a place to live; it encompasses a range of factors that affect students' daily lives and their ability to thrive academically and socially. Satisfaction in this context includes the quality of facilities, safety and security, location and accessibility, management practices and the social environment within the hostels. In the context of student housing in Nigerian universities, Ibem, Eziyi, Adeboye and Alagbe (2015) revealed that students' perceptions of on-campus housing facilities are largely shaped by the adequacy of the facilities, maintenance services, and the overall physical environment.

The rapid growth in student population has outpaced available accommodations and facilities, prompting private sectors to participate in student housing (Oladokun & Ojo, 2021). Due to increasing tertiary enrolment, the competition for available housing both on and off-campus has intensified, particularly in areas close to educational institutions. Students often come from various backgrounds, each with distinct expectations for comfort and amenities. As highlighted by Ojo (2023), mismatches between students' expectations and the realities of hostel life can lead to significant dissatisfaction, particularly among those from more affluent backgrounds.

Tenant satisfaction in students' hostels remains an important factor which poses a serious challenge to students at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka often prompting students to seek

alternative accommodation options which might reduce productivity in educational objectives among other expectations of these students.

Statement of the Problem

Research by Oke, Aigbavboa, and Raphiri, (2017) revealed that there are variety of features and management system in hostels that brings dissatisfaction to students in university-owned accommodations. Student hostels, which are critical for the academic success and overall well-being of students, often face issues related to quality, safety, and affordability. Despite efforts to improve these facilities, there remains a gap in understanding the specific needs and satisfaction of the student tenants in hostel accommodations, hence the study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Tenants Satisfaction

Gibler and Tyvima (2014) defined tenant satisfaction as a tenant's overall contentment with their housing situation, which encompasses physical aspects of the property, the quality of management services, and the surrounding environment. Satisfaction is influenced by both tangible factors example include building quality, amenities etc. and intangible factors example include sense of community, safety etc. It reflects the extent to which residents expectations and needs are met within their living environments. This concept is of paramount importance to the students/tenants, property/hostel managers, urban planners, and policymakers.

Oke, Aigbavboa, and Raphiri, (2017) revealed that some features that make students dissatisfied with university-owned accommodations include enforcement of rules that compels all students to move out with their belongings during each recess, the effectiveness of the lift system, the size of wardrobe and closet, laundry service in the residence, numbers of electrical sockets, window quality, neighborhood safety, overall building quality and services provided by residence management.

Students' Hostels

According to Johnson and Johnson (2012), Hostel accommodation refers to a residential facility that offers students a place to live during their academic tenure, often characterized by shared amenities and communal living arrangements aimed at fostering a conducive learning environment. They further explained that the communal nature of hostel life encourages cultural

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exchange and mutual support and friendships among students from diverse backgrounds. This inclusive environment enriches the overall university experience.

Adama, Aghimien and Fabunmi (2018) defined a student hostel as "a supervised living-learning residence for students, typically located within or near educational institutions, providing accommodation and often additional services to support academic pursuits." Hostels are typically located close to educational institutions to make it convenient for students to attend classes and access campus resources. They are designed with safety in mind, often including security measures and regulations set by the educational institution to ensure a secure living environment. Many hostel accommodations also provide amenities like study rooms, internet access, and recreational areas to support students' academic and social needs. The focus is on creating a supportive environment that helps students succeed academically while also enjoying a balanced social life. Student hostels vary widely in their structure and amenities. Some are large, purpose-built complexes housing hundreds of students, others are smaller, converted residential buildings. The quality and types of facilities can vary from basic shared rooms with communal bathrooms to more luxurious apartment-style accommodations with private facilities (Oke, Aigbavboa & Raphiri, 2017).

Public Hostels

The public hostels are often more affordable than other housing options outside the school premises. Brown (2016) opined that these hostels are designed to be cost-effective and are usually located close to campus. This proximity makes it easy for students to attend classes, use the library, and participate in campus activities without long commutes. Public hostels are typically funded, owned, and managed by government entities or public institutions, such as universities or municipal authorities. They are primarily designed to provide affordable housing options for specific groups, such as students, government employees, or individuals from low-income. Universities often regulate the public hostels within the campus to ensure they are safe and orderly. Common security measures include controlled access, surveillance cameras, and resident advisors to protect students and maintain discipline.

Studies revealed that on-campus students accommodation/ public hostels has generated more conflict between institutions authorities and the students body on the matters surrounding facilities provision, maintenance and services (Olukolajo and Mbazor 2021).

Private Hostels

Private hostels are often owned and managed by private individuals or companies. This type of hostel provide alternative to university-provided accommodation. According to Adama, Aghimien, and Fabunmi (2018), these hostels often provide a wider range of options, from basic shared rooms to more luxurious apartment-style units. They typically offer amenities such as private bathrooms, kitchens, and sometimes additional facilities like gyms or study areas. Private hostels are usually more expensive than public hostels but often provide better maintenance and more modern facilities. They may be located off-campus, requiring students to commute. Although private hostels provide more privacy and comfort, private hostels may lack the community atmosphere, security concerns and regulation of on-campus hostels. Furthermore, ownership structure influences management practices, with private hostels typically demonstrating greater operational efficiency and responsiveness to tenant needs (Nguyen & Smith, 2022). Private hostels remain an important part of the accommodation landscape in many countries, particularly in student-dominated regions.

Empirical Review

Several researchers have conducted studies in these aspect of tenants and students satisfaction generally both in private houses and students hostels providing valuable information into this significant area.

Abdullahi, Ibrahim and Zubair (2024) examined how landlord-tenant relationships influence tenant satisfaction in Kano. The study revealed that tenants who reported having open communication with their landlords and quick resolution of disputes were more satisfied. On the other hand, poor communication, delays in repairs, and disregard for tenants concerns negatively influenced satisfaction.

Ajibola and Bello (2022) examined the relationship between perceived security and tenant satisfaction in gated communities in Lagos. The study disclosed that while tenants generally felt safer in gated communities, their overall satisfaction was also influenced by the availability of social amenities, green spaces, and management efficiency.

Njuguna and Karanja (2022) investigated sanitation and hygiene in Kenyan public university hostels. The authors recommended that public universities prioritize improving hostel hygiene and sanitation to promote better student health and well-being.

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Eze and Onwuegbuchulam (2021) assessed tenant satisfaction in private hostels in Nigerian universities. The study assessed factors such as safety, amenities, and cost-effectiveness in determining the overall satisfaction of students living in private accommodations. The study recommended the need for private hostel owners to focus on maintaining a balance between affordability and quality service provision.

A study by Eze and Okafor (2020) focused on tenant satisfaction in private student hostels in Ifite-Awka. Their study shed light on the quality of facilities, proximity to campus, and security measures as major factors determining student satisfaction while overcrowding, inconsistent water and electricity supply led to significant dissatisfaction among student tenants.

Obi and Chika (2018) explored the impact of management practices on tenant satisfaction. Their work identified proactive maintenance services and timely resolution of complaints enhances tenant satisfaction in residential accommodations. Their study revealed that hostels with efficient management teams results in higher satisfaction rates.

METHODOLOGY

Population of the Study

Tenants occupying both public and private hostels were considered for the study in Awka Metropolis. However, the population of the study consists of a total number of students in the selected areas, which is Tempsite and Ifite-Awka to get a view from the opinions of the students in those areas as shown in table 1. Since the study required information on the satisfaction of students in the hostel, such information was therefore obtained from the students. The total population obtained from the selected public and private hostel in the study area was 4,252.

Table 1: Population of Students Selected in Both Public and Private Hostels

Selected Areas	Number of Students
Public	2860
Private	1,392
Total	4,252

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

The public and private hostels in the selected study area was sampled in other to generate a reliable data that can obtain a general view to the findings. The sample size was derived using Taro Yamane formula to obtain a good representation of the population.

To determine the sample size for the hostels, we used Yamane's formula:

$$n = N / (1 + N \times e^2)$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = total population size

e = level of significance (assumed 5% or 0.05 for this study)

Total population (N) = 4252

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2} = \frac{4252}{1 + 4252(0.05^2)} = \frac{4252}{1 + 10.63} = \frac{4252}{11.63} = 366$$

This chapter featured the analysis of data collected through the questionnaires during the field survey. Responses collected from the respondents was analyzed and interpreted in line with the research questions, which was formulated from the objectives of the study.

DISTRIBUTION AND COLLECTION OF QUESTIONNAIRES

Table 2 below shows the total number of questionnaires distributed, the number returned, and the percentage return. From the 366 questionnaires distributed to the respondents, 337 were returned. This represents a 92.7% return rate.

Table 2: Distribution and Return of Questionnaires

	Number Distributed	Number Returned	Number Unreturned	Percentage Returned (%)
Respondents	366	337	39	92.7

Demographic Features of Respondents

Table 3: Distribution of how Long Respondents have been staying in their Hostels

Duration	Frequency	Percent
Less than 6 months	29	8.6
6 months to 1 year	181	53.7
2-3 years	96	28.5
More than 3 years	31	9.2

From table 4 and figure 2, it can be seen that students reside in both private and public hostels. The respondents from the private hostel constitutes about 63.8 percent of the overall respondents while those of the public hostel constitutes about 36.2 percent.

Table 5: Distribution of Categories of Hostel Based on its Facilities and Services

Category	Frequency	Percent
Basic (Minimal facilities, shared amenities)	149	44.2
Standard (Moderate facilities, some private amenities)	158	46.9
Premium (Advanced facilities, private amenities)	30	8.9
Total	337	100.0

Figure 3: Categories of hostel based on its facilities and services

Table 5 and figure 3 show that about 44.2 percent of the respondents live in hostels with basic (minimal facilities and shared amenities), 46.9 percent live in standard (moderate facilities with some private amenities) while 8.9 percent live in premium (advanced facilities with private amenities). Table 6 shows the cross tabulation of the categories of the hostels (private and public) and their facilities.

Table 6: Cross Tabulation of “What is the category of your hostel?” and “How would you categorize your hostel based on its facilities and services?”

How would you categorize your hostel based on its facilities and services?			Total
Basic (Minimal facilities, shared amenities)	Standard (Moderate facilities, some private amenities)	Premium (Advanced facilities, private amenities)	

What is the Private category of hostel your hostel?	Count	69	119	27	215
	% of Total	20.5%	35.3%	8.0%	63.8%
Public hostel	Count	80	39	3	122
	% of Total	23.7%	11.6%	0.9%	36.2%
Total	Count	149	158	30	337
	% of Total	44.2%	46.9%	8.9%	100.0%

Table 6 shows that those living in private hostels which is 63.8 percent, about 20.5 percent of their hostels have basic (minimal facilities and shared amenities), 35.3 percent live in hostels standard (moderate facilities with some private amenities) while 8.0 percent live in premium (advanced facilities with private amenities). Furthermore, those living in public hostels which constitute about 36.2 percent, 23.7 percent of their hostels have basic (minimal facilities and shared amenities), 11.6 percent live in hostels standard (moderate facilities with some private amenities) while 0.9 percent lives in premium (advanced facilities with private amenities).

Research Question Two (2): What is the current level of tenant satisfaction in different student hostels in Awka?

Likert scales was used for this research question .The likert scales is thus explained; Very Dissatisfied=1; Dissatisfied=2; Neutral=3; Satisfied=4 and Very Satisfied=5 for the first question and Very Poor=1; Poor=2; Fair=3; Good=4 and Excellent=5. The Likert scales were used to obtain mean cutoff point as follows:

$$x = \frac{1+2+3+4+5}{5} = \frac{15}{5} = 3.0$$

The implication of the above mean cutoff point is that responses with mean value of 3.0 and above implies satisfied or good for 1 and 2 respectively while less than 3.0 implies dissatisfied or poor for 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 7: Current Level of Tenants Satisfaction in Students Hostels

S/N	Item	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	Remark
1	How satisfied are you with the responsiveness of hostel management to complaints or requests?	56	113	112	51	5	2.51	Dissatisfied
2	Room size and layout	37	66	130	75	29	2.98	Dissatisfied

3	Cleanliness and hygiene	43	82	108	81	23	2.88	Dissatisfied
4	Safety and security	32	65	105	73	62	3.20	Satisfied
5	Furniture and fittings quality	38	108	118	65	8	2.69	Dissatisfied
6	Noise levels	56	63	128	68	22	2.81	Dissatisfied
7	Availability and reliability of utilities (water, electricity, internet)	60	75	109	78	15	2.74	Dissatisfied
8	How satisfied are you with the communal facilities provided (kitchen, study areas, laundry, etc.)?	65	69	120	72	11	2.69	Dissatisfied
9	How would you rate the effectiveness of the maintenance services? (e.g., repairs)	45	97	125	70	0	2.65	Poor

Table 7 showed that the respondents are dissatisfied with the responsiveness of hostel management to complaints or requests, room size and layout, cleanliness and hygiene, furniture and fittings quality, noise levels, availability and reliability of utilities (like water, electricity, internet), the communal facilities provided (such as kitchen, study areas, laundry, etc.). Respondents were satisfied with safety and noted that security and the effectiveness of the maintenance services (e.g., repairs) is poor.

Research Question Three (3): What are the factors influencing tenant satisfaction in student hostels in Awka?

The Likert scales of this research question were structured using strongly disagree (SD=1), disagree (D=2), undecided (UN=3), agree (A=4) and strongly agree (SA=5), from which a mean cutoff point was calculated as follows:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{1+2+3+4+5}{5} = \frac{15}{5} = 3.0$$

From the cutoff point, a factor with a mean response of 3.0 is regarded as a factor that respondents agree to while a factor with a mean response less than 3.0 is regarded as a factor respondents disagree to.

Table 8: Factors Influencing Tenants Satisfaction in Students Hostels

S/N	Item	1	2	3	4	5	Mean	Remark
1	Room size and comfort	30	58	111	98	40	3.18	Agree
2	Cleanliness and hygiene	35	57	117	81	47	3.14	Agree
3	Safety and security	31	43	100	85	78	3.40	Agree
4	Quality of furniture and fittings	29	73	123	87	25	3.02	Agree
5	Noise levels	38	56	112	83	48	3.14	Agree
6	Availability of utilities (water, electricity, internet)	46	42	100	102	47	3.18	Agree

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7	Responsiveness of management	52	67	91	95	32	2.96	Disagree
8	Cost of accommodation	55	64	90	75	53	3.02	Agree
9	Promptness to request	53	79	114	54	37	2.83	Disagree
10	Proximity to campus or amenities	41	38	111	98	49	3.23	Agree

From table 8, it can be seen that the respondents agree that the following are the factors influencing tenant satisfaction in student hostels, which include the room size and comfort, cleanliness and hygiene, safety and security, quality of furniture and fittings, noise levels, availability of utilities (water, electricity, and internet), cost of accommodation and proximity to campus or amenities. On the other hand, respondents disagreed that responsiveness of management and promptness to request are factors influencing tenant satisfaction in student hostels.

Research Question Four (4): What are the identifiable areas that can improve the level of tenant satisfaction in students' hostel in Awka?

This research question was answered using the responses of question three above, where the respondents have given their views on the factors influencing tenant satisfaction in student hostels. This is because, if the factors noted can be improved upon, it will affect the level of tenant satisfaction in students' hostels.

These areas include; room size and comfort, cleanliness and hygiene, safety and security, quality of furniture and fittings, noise levels, availability of utilities (water, electricity, and internet), cost of accommodation and proximity to campus or amenities.

Interview Section

From the interview session conducted with the respondents living in private hostels, many students also complained of unclear hostel policies which include rent refunds, utility charges, rent review clause and caution fee. Furthermore, misunderstandings often arises due to lack of formal documentation or unbalanced tenancy agreement.

In addition, public hostels respondents opined that restrictions to privacy posed a major issue in the satisfaction of the students. The check-in procedures and visitor limitations can be inconvenient for students who wish to have guests, as they may need to plan visits around strict rules. This has deterred friends and family from visiting thereby reducing support network for students living in the public hostels.

SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Key Findings

- i.** The research on assessment of tenants' satisfaction in student hostels in Awka, Anambra State, provided a valuable insight into the types of hostel accommodation, available facilities, duration of stay, and factors affecting tenant satisfaction. A significant majority of respondents (63.8%) reside in private hostels, while a smaller segment (36.2%) lives in public hostels. In terms of amenities, around 44.2% of students are in hostels with basic facilities, 46.9% have access to standard amenities, and only 8.9% benefit from premium accommodations.
- ii.** The assessed facilities showed that those living in private hostels, 20.5% have basic setups, 35.3% have standard accommodations, and 8.0% enjoy premium conditions. Conversely, public hostels exhibit a higher proportion of basic facilities (23.7%), but fewer students (11.6%) have standard amenities, and only 0.9% have access to premium facilities.
- iii.** Satisfaction levels indicated notable dissatisfaction with various aspects of hostel living, which include room size and layout, cleanliness and hygiene, furniture quality, noise levels, and the reliability of utilities like water and electricity. Respondents also pointed out shortcomings in communal facilities such as kitchens and study areas. Nonetheless, they generally felt safe in their living environments, though concerns were raised about security and maintenance services.
- iv.** Qualitative data collated from interviews reveal additional challenges in private hostels. Respondents in private hostels expressed significant concerns regarding unclear hostel policies related to various aspects, including rent refunds, utility charges, rent review clause and caution fee. Many students reported that the lack of formal documentation or transparency in these policies often leads to misunderstandings and disputes between management and tenants. This ambiguity not only contributes to dissatisfaction but also creates an atmosphere of mistrust, where students feel their concerns are not taken seriously. By addressing these gaps and establishing clearer communication and documentation practices, management could significantly enhance tenant confidence and satisfaction.
- v.** Conversely, students living in public hostels identified privacy restrictions as a major issue affecting their satisfaction. The strict check-in procedures and limitations on visitors have

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led to feelings of isolation. Students are forced to plan their social interactions around these rigid rules, which detracts from their overall sense of freedom. The inability to host friends or family can limit their support networks during critical academic periods which adds to the stress of living in a public hostel.

Conclusion

In conclusion, satisfaction levels indicate significant concerns, particularly regarding management responsiveness (mean score of 2.51), room size and layout (mean of 2.98), cleanliness (mean of 2.88), furniture quality (mean of 2.69), noise levels (mean of 2.81), and utility reliability (mean of 2.74). Although respondents feel safe in their environments (mean of 3.20), they express dissatisfaction with other aspects, including the effectiveness of maintenance services (mean of 2.65). To enhance tenant satisfaction, the study identified key areas for improvement: which include increasing room comfort, ensuring cleanliness and hygiene, bolstering safety and security, upgrading furniture quality, minimizing noise levels, and providing reliable utilities. The research underscores the importance of enhancing management practices and facility quality to create a more satisfying living environment for students. These findings can inform future initiatives aimed at improving the accommodation experience for students and ultimately fostering a supportive and enriching atmosphere.

Recommendations

- i. Enhance Management Responsiveness:** It is essential to create effective communication channels that enable students to express their concerns and provide feedback easily. By establishing a system that ensures prompt attention to complaints and requests, management can cultivate a supportive atmosphere where students feel acknowledged and valued.
- ii. Improve Facility Quality:** Upgrading shared areas and amenities is vital for meeting students' diverse needs. This involves ensuring that communal spaces, such as kitchens, study rooms, and laundry facilities, are well-maintained and adequately equipped, thereby enhancing both comfort and functionality for student-tenants.
- iii. Focus on Cleanliness and Hygiene:** Maintaining high cleanliness standards is critical for tenant satisfaction. Implementing a regular cleaning schedule for both private and common

areas, alongside promoting good hygiene practices among students, will create a healthier and more pleasant living environment.

- iv. **Address Safety and Security Concerns:** Strengthening safety measures, such as improved lighting, security cameras, and controlled access points, can significantly enhance residents' sense of security. Educating students on safety protocols and emergency procedures will also ensure they are well prepared for any situation.
- v. **Optimize Room Size and Layout:** Reviewing and redesigning room layouts to maximize space and comfort is crucial for tenant satisfaction. Exploring options for more private accommodations or enhancing shared amenities can contribute to a more enjoyable living experience.
- vi. **Enhance Utility Services:** Ensuring the reliability of essential services like water, electricity, and internet is key to student satisfaction. Prioritizing regular maintenance and prompt repairs will help prevent service disruptions and maintain a comfortable living environment.
- vii. **Reduce Noise Levels:** Implementing strategies to minimize noise disturbances, such as soundproofing common areas and enforcing quiet hours can foster a more conducive living atmosphere. Promoting a culture of respect among student tenants regarding noise levels will also improve the overall experience.
- viii. **Review Accommodation Costs:** Conducting a comprehensive analysis of accommodation pricing can help ensure that costs align with the quality of facilities and services offered. Additionally, providing financial assistance or flexible payment options for students in need can enhance accessibility.
- ix. **Promote Proximity to Campus Amenities:** Emphasizing the advantages of living in hostels that are conveniently located near campus and essential services can attract more residents. Additionally, collaborating with local businesses to offer discounts or special deals for hostel residents can enrich their living experience.
- x. **Establishing clearer communication and documentation practices:** This involves creating transparent policies regarding rent, utility charges, and other hostel regulations. Management should ensure that all policies are documented in an easily accessible format, to minimize misunderstandings and disputes.

- xi. **Flexible Policies:** By reassessing and potentially relaxing restrictions, the students tenants could create a more welcoming and supportive environment that fosters social connections among students residing in these hostels.

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